

Organometallic Complexes. Part III. A Conductometric Study of Sulphanilamide Complexes with Li, Na, K, Cu and Ag

Kamal K. Chaturvedi and R. Kaushal

The Sulphanilamide complexes with Li, Na, K, Cu and Ag are shown to be formed in the ratio of 1 : 1 by Conductometry. Application of Job's method to the complexes of Li, Cu and Ag also gave the metal-ligand ratio 1 : 1.

Sulphanamides of the structure have been found to form complexes with metals. For example, sulphanilamide and prontosil form complexes with copper¹ and 3 : 5 dibromo-

sulphanilamide reacting with mercuric chloride form mercury² complex. A green copper chelate with mono-paratoluene sulphonyl derivative of ortho-phenylene diamine has been described by Bilman and co-workers³. This ligand has been shown to be a specific reagent for the estimation of copper.

In part I⁴ and II⁵ of the series some mercury-sulphonamide complexes have been described, in which the mercuric acetate is shown to bring about metalation in the heterocyclic or the aromatic ring of the sulphonamide molecule and that the heterocyclic ring is preferentially metalated. Some of these mercury complexes are shown to possess enhanced activity as compared to the parent drugs. Ghosh and Majumdar⁶ have used benzene sulphonyl-glycines as complexing agents for metals and have shown that the imido-hydrogen becomes more acidic on the formation of metal-nitrogen coordinate bond. Thus, the sulphonamides containing $-SO_2 - NH -$ group seem to be good complexing agents. Therefore, a systematic investigation of their complexes with other metals has been undertaken. In the present communication the conductometric studies of some metal (Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Cu^{++} , and Ag^+) complexes with the parent sulphanilamide are described.

1. G. Mararovici, *Bull. Soc. Stiinte Chug.*, 1940, **9**, 426.
2. Rango and Solarino, *Gazzetta*, 1941, **71**, 235.
3. J. H. Bilman, N. S. Aantos and R. Charmin, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 1342.
4. K. K. Pandey and R. Kaushal, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **32**, 94.
5. S. Siddiqui and R. Kaushal, communicated for publication.
6. N. N. Ghosh and M. N. Majumdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 945; 1966, **43**, 545; 1967, **44**, 559.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents : Pure sulphanilamide (M.P. 165.5°). Analar grade BDH lithium carbonate, sodium acetate, potassium acetate, copper sulphate and silver nitrate. Fresh solution of the sulphanilamide and different salts were prepared in double distilled water.

The conductance measurements were carried out with conductivity bridge (WTW, German make) using dip-type conductivity cell at 30°.

The results of titration of the different metal solutions ($M/50$) with 10 ml of $M/100$ ligand diluted to 200 ml. to eliminate volume corrections are plotted in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1. Metal ml = 10 mm x 1 cm.

Job's method of continuous variation was also used for Li, Cu and Ag using $M/50$ solutions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Figure 1 are shown the plots of conductance versus volume of the metal solution. From the curves for Li, Na, K, Cu and Ag respectively the ratio of these metals to sulphanilamide is found to be 1 : 1 in all cases.

Further, in case of Li, Cu and Ag, Job's method of continuous variation was employed using conductance as the index property. Here again, the ratio of Li, Cu and Ag to sulphanilamide is found to be 1 : 1.